

PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY DIRECTED TO SOCIALIZATION OF STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF GENDER APPROACH

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Abstract: In this thesis, Opinions about professional activities based on the gender approach in the socialization of students were discussed.

Key words: psychological, gender approach, cortex, concept, educational system, model, socialization.

Introduction:

System of social education of higher education students: Designing theorization of social education as the most important component of the education system was observed in the 90 years. This position, according to T. A. Romm, is related to the fact that the highlighted phenomenon is the most important direction of education, claiming to form the field of social and pedagogical knowledge. It is known that education as an individual independent aspect is not effective. It is necessary to talk about the educational system, which has a decisive influence on the formation of personality.

Considering the organization of the educational process as a system, attempts to determine the principles of structure and conditions affecting the development of the system from the point of view of a systematic approach (hierarchy, comparison, integrity) were made long ago by Ya.A. Comenius Considered by, J. Locke, A. S. Makarenko and others.

The lack of a generally accepted definition of the term "system", in our opinion, is due, on the one hand, to the existence of various criteria that implement a systematic approach in author's works. On the other hand, there are detailed ideas about different types of education systems. In the systematic approach, the attention of researchers is focused not only on the integrity of the phenomenon under consideration, but also on its composition, the characteristics of the elements manifested in their interaction.

In a narrow sense, L. Bertalanfi defines a system as a complex of interacting elements¹. This definition does not reflect the important features of the system. According to the philosophical dictionary, a system (from the Greek systema - made up of parts, united) is a category denoting an object organized as a whole, where the energy of connection between the elements of the system exceeds the

¹ Л. фон Бергаланфи. Общая теория систем—обзор проблем и результатов. —М.: Системные исследования, 1969. —С. 41-45.

energy of their connection with the elements of other systems. In a broader sense, a system is the unity and integrity of interrelated elements.

Referring to the dictionary of the Russian language edited by S. I. Ozhegov, N. Shvedova, we can conclude that this concept is expressed as many elements in relationships and connections with each other that form a certain integrity, unity². However, this definition is not sufficient to fully describe the system. In our opinion, the most successful definition leads to the idea of P. K. Anokhin: the system is such a set of selectively involved components that have a goal-oriented character, aimed at obtaining a useful result, focused only on interaction and relations. If we consider the holistic educational process in the context of this definition, then it is very important that each component (element) interacts to obtain a targeted result, that is, the student becomes a future teacher, determines the level of knowledge as a pedagogical labor specialist.

Analysis of scientific literature shows that there are several hundred interpretations of the concept of system. Highlight the main features and characteristics of the system used in the existing definitions:

- any system has its own boundaries with the environment (limited);
- the properties of the whole system cannot be reduced to the sum of the properties of its elements (integrity);
 - the behavior of the system is mainly related to the characteristics (structure) of its structure;
 - the system develops only under the condition of constant interaction with the environment (connection with the environment);
 - all elements in the system are very closely subordinated to each other (hierarchy);
 - the system is able to complicate its structure during the life cycle (self-development);
- any system is an element of another, more complex system, giving it certain properties (unit);
- the life cycle of any system includes the time of its existence: birth, youth, maturity, old age, death (ontogenetics);
 - the complexity and diversity of the existing systems in the universe require a large number of their descriptions (multiplicity of descriptions).

According to many researchers, the system is a whole unit consisting of complementary and interrelated elements (parts), where each of them brings a new particle to the specific characteristics of the whole. It follows that the

² Ожегов, С. И. Словарь русского языка: 70 000 слов / под ред. Н. Ю. Шведовой. 23-е изд., испр. —М.: Русский язык, 1990. —917 с.

specific features of the system are integral qualities that ensure the integrity of the organism; creating conditions to separate it from the external environment. Then an elementary (indivisible) particle is a hierarchically organized collection as a basis for building a system. In the context of pedagogical sciences, the system is considered as an ordered set of interrelated elements that are separated on the basis of certain characteristics, united by the common goal of the operation and unity of management, and act as an integral phenomenon in interaction with the environment. The educational system can be seen as a complex open social system that is synergistically related to other systems of society and affects the development of human personality³.

According to T. A. Romm, the systematic approach in social education works in the context of subject analysis, which allows to determine the generality of interrelated components. It provides a functional analysis that describes social education in relation to other phenomena of social life, and a historical analysis that demonstrates a genetic analysis of social education as a socio-cultural system. Analyzing the phenomenon of the system, it is necessary to consider the concept of the educational system. This is related to the impact of the systematic approach on the theoretical positions and practical embodiment of the educational process. The specified approach is universal, widely used in theoretical and applied sciences, modern management.

In our opinion, the appeal to this concept arises from some contradictions that exist in the educational system:

1. The growing need of the developing society to form a person with physical, mental, social and spiritual health, high creative potential and technocratic and technological practice of education.

2. The state educational standards declare the necessity of forming a specialist with high professional competences and not paying enough attention to his humanitarian and spiritual-ethical development.

3. With the introduction of a new generation into the state educational standard, the requirements for the implementation of the bachelor's basic educational program are necessary for the comprehensive development of a person and the preparation of a narrowly specialized graduate of a university working in a certain profession or specialty creating a social and cultural environment.

4. Introduction of general cultural and professional competences aimed at socio-cultural, spiritual and moral education of the student and lack of a clear

³ Ахмедова, З. К. Идеи рыцарского воспитания в истории педагогической мысли таджиков: автореф. дис. ... канд. пед. наук. — Душанбе, 2011. —25 с.

model of a graduate of higher education in accordance with the published standards of the third generation.

5. Author ideas in pedagogical communities, the presence of developments that allow the creation of innovative educational systems, and the weakening of the role of the state in supporting the education sector.

The actual systems that exist in society, including social learning, are open. Therefore, it is recommended to work with the concept of *sotsialnaya* social system *ponyat*, which works in accordance with the laws of the development of society. Any social system is inextricably linked with: macrosociety, that is, the whole system of society; environment, including a pedagogical university, a microsociety that acts as a factor, condition and mechanism of educational influence on a person.

The analysis of the concept of the Vospit educational system confirms the opinion about the ambiguity of the interpretation of the essence, structure and functions of the Vospit educational system. Thus, in the pedagogical vocabulary of G. M. Kojaspirova, the vospit educational system means the sum of the following interrelated components: educational goals, people, those who implement them, their activities, the relationships that arise between participants, developed environment and management activities to ensure the viability of the educational system. This definition, in our opinion, is the most common, although it does not fully reflect the composition of the system.

From the point of view of V.A. Slastenin, the educational system is a complex social psychological and pedagogical education that is unequal, self-directed and controlled. This means that in the process of activity, the educational system is able to change its structure and content after achieving a certain educational goal.

In the context of N.V. Bordovskaya and A.A. Rean, this phenomenon is focused on the technological component and is presented as a set of interrelated goals and principles, methods, techniques for fulfilling the social order.

Thus, according to E.N. Stepanov, the educational system is an ordered set of interrelated components, the interaction of which helps to implement functions that contribute to the development of a person in an educational institution will give. V.S. Kukushin presents the educational system as a group of components of social reality that ensures the spiritual and moral formation and creative development of a person. Yu.S. Manuilov defines the educational system

in terms of interaction with the environment aimed at ensuring positive development and formative influence⁴.

It follows from the above definitions that the educational system can be understood as a certain form of regulation of the entire life of the university in relation to the function of educating students. In its expanded form, it combines all types of activities in the educational process on the basis of universal values, norms, customs and educational goals, self-education, self-education, self-development of the individual acts as a stable unity that creates favorable conditions for its development. According to our research, the concept of the educational system is a link aimed at self-improvement, self-development, personality development in accordance with the rules and norms of behavior accepted in modern society viewed as an ordered collection of distinct and interacting elements.

Studying the experience of these talented teachers shows that the system-forming factor of the education and training system was a humanistic orientation to the human personality, reflecting the high spiritual and moral instructions of the culture. The words of V. A. Slavenin "the teacher does not educate, does not teach, but renews, stimulates the desire of the student to develop himself, studies his activity, creates conditions for self-movement." It is appropriate to quote them.

The analysis of psychological, pedagogical, scientific and methodical sources shows that the mechanism of development and implementation of educational systems for secondary general education is more developed. Thus, from the point of view of L. I. Novikova, the educational system as a whole organism represents the unity of administrative and creative elements.

A characteristic feature of higher education systems is, first of all, the direction of its professional activity. Accordingly, the following factors should be taken into account when modeling the pedagogical higher education system:

- the social order of the state expressed in educational standards: professional teacher training;
- specific pedagogical higher educational potential (educational traditions, level of training of higher education teachers for educational activities, availability of methodological material, etc.).

Based on these rules, it is necessary to recognize that the educational system in each educational institution is individual. Its specific features depend on the type of educational institution, the quantitative and gender composition

⁴ Мануйлов, Ю. С. Средовый подход в воспитании: автореф. дис. ... д-ра пед. наук. —М., 1997. —49 с.

of students, their nationality, and social weight. The characteristics of the educational system are determined by the social (state) order of the society, the material and technical base of the university; the structure of the educational institution (number of faculties, characteristics of each faculty), characteristics of the environment, etc.

Note that in addition to definitions such as system and educational system, the systemic approach is represented by the following concepts: systematicity (the presence of integral properties), component (an integral part of the system), element (unit of the system), structure (the structure of the object a set of elements and connections between them that ensure its integrity), communication (the existence of interdependence), a system-forming factor (ensures the maintenance and balance of the system, serves as a source of its unity and activity). It should be noted that the specified elements of the set that make up the system are in certain relations and connections with each other and form a structure. The systemic approach not only determines the methods of defining and describing these relationships and connections, but also distinguishes the main ones that make up the system, which ensures the integrity of the system, its development.

The terminological analysis of the concept of the educational system showed that there are common views on the problem under study:

- the educational system is purposeful, open, values-oriented and helps to educate a person according to the set goals;
- the educational system is self-developing and self-managing (capable of setting goals, designing a new situation, correcting educational processes);
- the educational system is social, and its activities are carried out in accordance with the laws of social development;
- the educational system is a complex structure, there are relationships, subsystems; characterized by hierarchy.
- the educational system is effective when there is control of the sequence of actions on the selection of appropriate educational procedures. The implementation of these procedures and effects ensures the transition and change of the educational system to the desired state.

I must say that the description of artificial systems (made by man) involves determining the location of the factors of determining goals. This means that there are objective systems and random systems, where factors can be inside the system, and factors outside the system. Targeted systems are able to choose a pattern of behavior depending on the selected target. This is not typical for

stochastic systems, since the objective function is determined by external factors.

Drawing a parallel between the higher education system and the concept of systems, we find that it can be included in the category of large systems that have the following characteristics according to a number of characteristics: expediency, flexibility, dynamism, mobility, prognosticity, multifactoriality and many criteria.

It is clear that the basis of any social system, including the educational system, is the basic principles, that is, the initial rules for studying and changing the objects of the system. Creating the theoretical basis of the organized process, they are the basis of the model of self-organization and self-development. The analysis of the resource base that studies the methodological aspects of creating social systems made it possible to highlight the following principles.

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